

Response of rainfed rice to farmyard manure placement and soil compaction

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We studied the response of rainfed rice (VRS163) to farmyard manure (FYM) incorporated at 10-cm soil depth, placed in 10-cm deep furrows, and placed

10 cm below soil surface. Two levels of soil compaction — no compaction (bulk density of 1.36 g/cm³) and interrow compaction (bulk density of 1.54 g/cm³) — also were studied.

The soil was a silt loam with 0.93% organic C and available moisture content of 14% (wt/wt). The crop received a basal dose of 40-18-33 kg NPK/ha. Rice was sown 5 Jul 1985 in rows 23 cm apart. Manure was applied at 10 t/ha.

Yields were significantly higher with

surface incorporation and placement at 10-cm depth (see table). Interrow soil compaction increased yield 9%. Weed growth was reduced by about 64% in soil compacted plots.

Surface layer soil moisture retention was increased by soil compaction and FYM placement (see figure). Profile moisture in the compacted plots was about 2 cm higher than in the uncompacted plots. ☞

Influence of soil compaction and FYM placement on yield and weed growth. Almora, India.

	Yield (t/ha)		Weed growth (g/m ²)	
	Not compacted	Compacted	Not compacted	Compacted
No manure	1.86	2.04	20.2	7.5
Manure incorporated at 10 cm	2.14	2.36	21.7	7.5
Manure furrow-placed	2.01	2.04	19.0	6.7
Manure placed 10 cm deep	2.19	2.34	18.2	6.9
CD 5%		Grain	Weed	
Compaction		ns	5.62	
FYM placement		0.26	1.65	
Interaction		ns	ns	

Soil water content at 70 d after sowing with compaction and FYM placement. Almora, India.

Improved management of urea in rice

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Experiments on N fertilizer management were conducted for four seasons (1983-85 kharif and summer 1984) on red sandy loam soil (Alfisols). The soil had pH 6.5, 0.65% organic C, 16.1 kg available P/ha, and 230 kg available K/ha. Loss of N through volatilization (static trap method) and leaching (using soil water samples tubes) was determined in the field. Test variety was IR20. The crop was raised using all the recommended practices under irrigated conditions. Neem cake-coated urea (NCCU) used (32% N) was prepared in a locally fabricated machine by using dehydrated neem cake (30% urea by weight) and a one-part coal tar (1% urea by weight) and 2 parts

Effect of improved management of urea on yield.^a Mandya, India.

Treatment ^b	N loss (kg/ha)	N uptake (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)
Recommended practice: 100 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits (50-25-25)	31.3	78.3	4.6
Improved practice: 80 kg N/ha through NCCU, all basal	20.7	84.1	5.4
Improved practice: 80 kg N/ha through 80% N as NCCU basal followed by 20% N as urea topdressed at tillering	16.2	96.3	6.1
No N (control)	8.8	44.1	2.7
'F' Test		**	**
CD (0.01)		15.2	0.6
CV (%)		9.3	10.1

^aAv of 4 seasons. ^bAll treatments received 22 kg P as single superphosphate and 41 kg K/ha as muriate of potash.

kerosene oil solution (available locally). NCCU significantly reduced N loss (34%) and increased yield (17%) as a consequence of better uptake (7%) of N. The result was a 20% savings in fertilizer over the recommended practice (see table). Efficiency increased substantially with 80% N applied as

NCCU, basal, followed by 20% N as prilled urea topdressed at tillering. N losses were significantly less (48%) and yields higher (32%) because of higher N uptake (23%), resulting in 20% savings in the fertilizer over the recommended practice. ☞